

CLIENT-TO-CLIENT STREAMING SCHEME FOR VoD APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose an efficient client-to-client streaming approach to cooperatively stream the video using chaining technique with unicast communication among the clients. This approach considers two major issues of VoD 1) Prefix caching scheme to accommodate more number of videos closer to client, so that the request-service delay for the user can be minimized. 2) Cooperative proxy and client chaining scheme for streaming the videos using unicasting. This approach minimizes the client rejection rate and bandwidth requirement on server to proxy and proxy to client path. Our simulation results show that the proposed approach achieves reduced client waiting time and optimal prefix caching of videos minimizing server to proxy path bandwidth usage by utilizing the client to client bandwidth, which is occasionally used when compared to busy server to proxy path bandwidth.

KEYWORDS

Prefix Caching, Cooperative Clients, Streaming, Bandwidth Usage, Chaining.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since streaming of any multimedia object like high quality video consumes a significantly large amount of network resources, network bandwidth limitation is the major constraint in most of the multimedia systems. So request-to-service delay, network traffic, congestion and server overloading are the main parameters to be considered in video streaming over the communication networks that affect the quality of service (QoS). Providing video-on-demand (VoD) service over the internet in a scalable way is a challenging problem. The difficulty is twofold: First, it is not a trivial task to stream video on an end-to-end basis because of a video's high bandwidth requirement and long duration. Second, scalability issues arise when attempting to service a large number of clients. In particular, a popular video generally attracts a large number of users that issues requests asynchronously [1].

There are many VoD schemes proposed to address these problems: patching, batching, periodical broadcasting, prefix caching and chaining.

In batching [6,8], the server makes the batches of requests for the same video together if their time of arrival are closer, and multicasts the video to these requests to save the network I/O bandwidth. In patching [2], the main server sends the complete video clip to the first client. Later clients join the existing multicast channel and get the missing data of the video using unicast channels. Another innovative technique is periodical broadcasting [9]. In this approach, popular videos are partitioned into a series of segments and these segments are continually broadcasted on several dedicated channels. Before clients start playing the videos, they usually have to wait for a time length equivalent to the first segment. Therefore, only near VoD service is provided.

Another promising approach to improve the bandwidth consumption issue is proxy caching [1, 4, 5]. In this approach, there exists a proxy between a central server and client clouds. Partial

video (or entire video) files are stored in proxies and the rest are stored in the central server. Proxies send cached videos to clients and request the remaining portion of the video from servers on behalf of clients.

In [3] researchers have proposed a region based hybrid algorithm for chaining, in which they reject the requests of different regions of the same proxy server, due to which rejection rate may be high. R Ashok Kumar et al.[12] have proposed a streaming scheme, in which rejection rate is very high until number of chains increases for the video. Hyunjoo and Heon in [10] have proposed another chaining scheme with VCR operations. Here they do stream the video data from main server, but they consider constant threshold value, due to which more number of clients may not be able to share the same chain, hence increasing the rejection rate.[6,8] proposes a batching technique called extended chaining (HEC), which unfairly forces the requests arriving early in a batch to wait for the latecomers. As a result, the reneging rate can be high in a system which employs this technique. To reduce the long access latency and client rejection ratio, in this paper we propose, a prefix caching based new client-to-client chaining mechanism for distributed VoD system to achieve the reduced client waiting time and the client request-rejection ratio.

This architecture for this approach consists of a centralized multimedia server [CMS] which is connected to distributed proxy servers. To each of the proxy server a cloud of users are connected.

The organization of rest of the paper is as follows: Section 2 discusses the system Model and the analysis of various parameters used in the model. In section 3 we present a proposed streaming algorithm in detail, the simulation model and performance evaluations are presented in Section 4. The section 5 presents the conclusions and the further work.

2. SYSTEM MODEL

The parameters considered for the model are shown in table 1. Let N be a stochastic variable representing the group of videos and it may take the different values (videos) for V_i ($i=1,2 \dots N$). we assume that the client's requests arrive according to Poisson process with the arrival rate λ . Let S_i be the size (duration in minutes) of i^{th} video ($i=1..N$) with mean arrival rates $\lambda_1 \dots \lambda_N$ respectively that are being streamed to the users using proxy server (PS). PS has a caching buffer large enough to cache total B minutes of K number of video prefixes.

Table 1. Parameters of the System Model

Parameter	Definition
N	Total number of videos
V_i	i^{th} video ($i=1..N$)
S_i	The size(minutes) of i^{th} video($i=1..N$)
λ_i	mean arrival rate of i^{th} video
PS	proxy server
$(Pref-I)$	W_I minutes video of V_i
B	Total size (minutes) of Proxy buffer
K	Total number of videos at PS
W	Size (Minutes) of (pref-1)

To increase the video availability rate at LPSG, The complete video is divided into two parts. Part1; first W_I minutes of each video V_i is referred to as $(pref)_i$ of V_i and is cached in any one of the proxy servers of the group only once.

Part2; remaining portion of the video V_i is referred to as suffix of V_i .

$$\text{i.e. } B = \sum_{i=1}^K (pref)_i$$

Based on the frequency of user requests to any video, the popularity of the videos and size of *prefix* to be cached at *PS* are determined. The size (*W*) of (*pref*) for *i*th video is determined as follows.

$$W(\text{pref})_i = x_i \times S_i \text{ where } 0 < x_i < 1$$

Where x_i is the probability of occurrence of user requests with frequency for video i from last t minutes. This arrangement allows the *PS* to cache maximum portion of more number of most frequently requesting videos. Hence most of the requests can be served immediately from *PS* itself, which reduces the request-service delay for the user [$(\text{Req-Ser})_{\text{delay}}$] and network bandwidth requirement on server-proxy path [BW^{S-P}] significantly.

The other output stochastic variable considered is R_{rej} . It is the request rejection ratio, which is the ratio of the number of requests rejected (N_{rej}) to total number of requests arrived at the system (R), which is inversely proportional to the system throughput S_{eff} , where $S_{\text{eff}} = \frac{Q}{R}$ is the ratio of number of requests served (Q) to total number of requests arrived (R) at the system as shown in the figure 1. The optimization problem is to maximize S_{eff} by minimizing the client rejection ratio R_{rej} , average Request-service delay and average bandwidth usage is.

Maximize System Efficiency $S_{\text{eff}} = \frac{Q}{R}$

Minimizing

- Avg WAN Bandwidth usage

$$BW^{S-P} = \sum_{i=1}^Q bw(S - (\text{pref}))_i^{S-P}$$

- Avg Request-service delay for the user

$$(\text{Req-Ser})_{\text{delay}} = \frac{1}{Q} \sum_{i=1}^Q (\text{Req-Ser})_{\text{delay}}$$

- Avg Request-rejection ratio

$$R_{\text{rej}} = N_{\text{rej}}/R$$

Subject to

$$B = \sum_{i=1}^K (\text{pref} - 1)_i, \quad W(\text{pref}) > 0$$

Figure 1 System Simulation Model

3. PROPOSED STREAMING ALGORITHM

3.1. Distributed VoD Algorithm

The distributed VoD architecture considered in this approach is as shown in figure 2. This architecture consists of a *CMS*, which is connected to a set of *PSs*. Each *PS* has various modules such as, *Interaction Module of PS (IM)*–Interacts with the client. *Service Manager (Ser-mgr)* –Manages the streaming of the videos. *Request handler*–Handles the requests from the user, *Client Manager (CM)* – Observes and updates the popularity of videos at PS. *SCL - streaming clients list* is the list with complete details of list of videos being streamed from that PS and the corresponding active chain of clients for that video. To each of these PSs a large number of users are connected. Each proxy is called as a parent proxy (PP) to its clients. Each client has various modules such as, *Buffer-manager*–buffers the video data received at the *Buffer*. *Media Player* –plays the buffered video. *Client Agent*– Performs the Communication with PS and other clients. *LAC – List of Applicant clients* – received from the PS. This is the list of d applicant clients of the active chain of the video, from whom a requested client can get the requested video stream.

The *PS* caches the prefix of videos distributed by *VDM*, and streams this cached portion of video to the client upon the request through *LAN* using its less expensive bandwidth. We assume that, proxies and their clients are closely located with relatively low communication cost [1]. The main central multimedia server in which all the videos completely stored is placed far away from PS, which involves high cost remote communication. The *CMS* and the *PSs* are assumed to be interconnected through high capacity optic fibre cables.

Figure 2 Distributed VoD Architecture

3.2. Proposed Streaming Algorithm

The main goal of our proposed streaming scheme is to make each client act as a server while it receives the video, so that the available memory and bandwidth of the clients can be utilized more efficiently. The un-scalability of traditional client-server unicast VoD service lies in the fact that the server is the only contributor and can thus become flooded by a large number of clients submissively requesting the service. In the client-server service model, the client sets up a direct connection with the server to receive the video. In this case an amount of network bandwidth requirement on server-proxy path equal to the playback rate is consumed along the route. As the number of requests

increases, the bandwidth at the server and the network is heavily consumed, due to which network becomes congested and the incoming requests are eventually rejected [2]. In contrast, we propose two schemes to address these issues 1) prefix caching technique reduces the request-service delay for the user and an amount of bandwidth consumption between client and main server. 2) Streaming scheme, where the clients not only receive the requested stream, but also contribute to the overall VoD service by forwarding the stream to other clients, whose request arrives within the threshold time of $W(pref)$. In this streaming approach all the clients are treated as potential server points. When there is a request for a video V_i from the client C_k at a proxy server PS , if the requested video V_i is present at PS , then the service will be provided to C_k in the following stages

3.2.1. Client admission phase

When the request arrives at PS_q , the *Request-handler* (*Req-handler*) of that proxy checks for the presence of the video at PS_q . If it is present then it checks the flag *IS-STREAMING* of the video V_i . If it is not true indicates that, there are no clients existing having streamed with the same video object. Then the *Req-handler* informs the *Ser-mgr* to provide the streaming of V_i to C_k . The *Ser-mgr* starts a new stream creating a new active chain for V_i and updates the streaming *clients list* (*SCL*) by adding a new entry for the video V_i along with its (*pref-1*) size and making *IS-STREAMING* flag of V_i true. The format of each entry of *SCL* is $\langle video\ id - sz(pref-1) - clients\ list\ being\ streamed\ with\ V_i \rangle$. If the flag *IS-STREAMING* is true, indicating that there are already a chain of clients being streamed with the same video. Then the *Req-handler* looks into the corresponding entry for V_i in *SCL* to check whether the inter arrival time difference of the new client and other clients of the existing active chain of V_i is below the threshold $T=W(pref-1)$, if so C_k is added to the existing chain of V_i and sends the *sub list of d applicant clients* (*LAC*: list of all $C_j \mid ((t_{C_j} - t_{C_k}) \leq W(pref-1)_{V_i}) j=1..d$) to C_k , along with the *msg* to get streamed from any of the client from the list(*LAC*). *Req-handler* also sends the message (*msg*) to all d clients of *LAC*, so that the *client agent* of these clients, who are ready to become *parent client* (*PC*) of C_k sends ready signal to C_k indicating that they are ready to stream the video. Then C_k sends *Ok-start* signal to the selected client C_j , which is comparatively more closer ($D(C_k, C_j)$: distance between C_k and C_j is minimum for all $j=1..d$) and also most recently being streamed with V_i , then C_k starts receiving the stream. This client C_j becomes the *PC* of C_k . Fig 3 shows this scenario, where we have active chains for two videos (56 and 14). Here when the client $C4$ requests for the video-56, it gets the *LAC* with $C1, C2$ and $C3$ but $C4$ decides to get the video stream from $C1$ as the $D(C4, C1)$ is comparatively minimum. In case any problem with this client, C_k can request the other clients of *LAC*. This reduces the *PS* involvement during playback. At the end of this client admission phase, *SCL* will have the complete details of list of videos being streamed and the corresponding chain of clients of each video. Also each client knows its applicant ancestors to change its *parent client* (*PC*) in case of any problem with the *PC*.

If V_i is not present at PS then *IM* coordinates with *CMS* and downloads the V_i , then is streamed to C_k . While streaming the $W(pref)$ of V_i is calculated and cached at PS , if sufficient space is available. Otherwise the dynamic buffer allocation algorithm [16] is executed to make room to cache this prefix of V_i according to popularity. In this case the request-service delay may be high, but the probability of downloading the complete video from the *CMS* is very less as shown by our simulation results. This approach allows most of the requests to be served immediately from the client of the active chain of the video, which is already being served from the PS and hence reduces the *client rejection-request ratio* R_{rej} , *server bandwidth usage*, and *request-service delay* for the user.

Whenever the sufficient buffer and bandwidth is not available in the above operation the user request is rejected.

Fig. 4 chain of video-56 c1-c2-c3-c4
chain of video-14 c1-c2-c3-c4-c5

Algorithm

At Proxy server (PS_q)

When a request from the client C_k for V_i arrives at time t to a particular proxy PS , the following steps are done.

If ($V_i \in PS$)

Checks the *SCL*

If (*IS-STREAMING* $_{V_i}$ is *TRUE*) // V_i has an Active chain

{
 create a list of all $C_j : j=1..d$
 such that $((t_{C_j} - t_{C_k}) \leq (pref)_{V_i})$ where $j=1..d$
 (*Req-hdtr*) $_{PS}$ sends *msg* with *LAC* to C_k
 }

else (*Ser-mgr* starts the new stream to C_k and updates *SCL*)

else pass the *Req* to *CMS*

download the V_i from *CMS*

If ($(pref)_{V_i} = (x_i \times S_i)$ can be cached at *PS*)

{ cache the $(pref)_{V_i}$ & Start new stream to C_k , &
 update *SCL* }

else

{ use Dynamic buffer allocation algorithm[ref.16] to make
 room to cache $(pref)_{V_i}$

If (sufficient buffer is not obtained)

Reject the request

3.2.2. Streaming phase

We assume that the client has sufficient buffer space and network bandwidth to accommodate the (pref) of V_i . Whenever the client C_k requests for V_i if the client is successfully admitted to the existing chain of V_i then it immediately starts getting the stream from the selected client from the LAC, the *buffer manager (buf-mgr)* starts buffering the video clips received from its PC. And *media-player* starts playing it from the buffer.

Client C_k

C_k sends the request to PS for the video V_i

when (C_k receives a msg with LAC from $(req-hdlr)_{PS}$)

C_k checks for the distance $D(C_k, C_j)$ with all $j=1..d$

Select C_j | $D(C_k, C_j)$ is minimum &

$((t_{C_j} - t_{C_k}) \leq W(pref)_{V_i})$

Send Ok-Start signal to C_j

Start getting streamed with the video.

else rejected

3.2.3 .Closing Phase

Any client C_k in the chain may want to terminate the connection in the following two cases

Case1: Once the streaming of the entire video is finished. The *client agent* of C_k has to terminate the connection with its *parent client (PC)* by sending termination signal to it, but checks whether this client is PC for any other clients in the chain before sending termination signal to its *parent proxy server(PPS)*. If so, it waits until the streaming of the whole video to its *child client (CC)* finishes or it may connect its CC to PC as explained in case2 and then sends the termination signal to its PPS and then terminates the connection. The *service-mgr* updates the SCL by removing the entry corresponding to terminated client from SCL.

Case2: In the middle of the streaming, if the C_k wants to stop watching the video, *client-agent* of C_k checks whether it is a parent for any other client in the chain. If so it checks whether $(t_{pc}(C_k) - t_{cc}(C_k))_{V_i} < (pref)_{V_i}$ is true, where $t_{pc}(C_k)$ is the arrival time of PC of C_k and $t_{cc}(C_k)$, is the arrival time of CC of C_k . if true it sends the termination signal to its PC, CC and PPS indicating that it is going to be terminated and also gives the details of its CC to its PC. So the PC of C_k can continue streaming to CC of C_k and informs PPS about the change of PC to CC of C_k . Then *service-mgr* of PPS updates the SCL by removing the entry for C_k in active client chain list of V_i

4. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

In our simulation model we have a single CMS and a group six PSs. Each of these PSs is connected to 50 users. We use the client request-rejection ratio, average server bandwidth usage and the average request-service delay for the user as parameters to measure the performance of our proposed approach more efficiently.

The table 2 lists the performance parameters considered for the simulation. Here we assume that the request distribution of the videos follows a zipf-like distribution. The user request arrival rate at each PS is 35-50 requests per hour. The ratio of cache sizes at CMS and PS is set to $C_{CMS} : C_{PS} = 10:2$ and transmission delay between the proxy and the client as 120 to 180 ms, transmission delay between the main server and the proxy as 480 ms to 640ms, transmission delay between client to client as 60 to 90 ms, the size of the cached (pref) of the video as 280MB to 1120MB(25min – 1hr) in proportion to its popularity.

Table 2. Parameters of Simulation Model

Notation	System Parameters	Default Values
BW_{s-p}	Server-proxy bandwidth	2 Gbps
BW_{p-c}	Proxy-client bandwidth	2 Mbps
BW_{c-c}	Client-client bandwidth	256 Kbps
S	Video Size	2-3hrs, 200units/hr
C_{CMS}	Cache Size(CMS)	1000
C_{PS}	Cache Size(PS)	200(15%)
A	Mean request arrival rate	44 reqs/hr

The results of average of several simulations conducted are shown below.

Figure 5 client rejection rate with time

Figure 6 Request-service delay V/s Time

Figure 5 shows the client rejection ratio of our proposed system, which is very less, as our streaming scheme allows more number of clients to join the active chain immediately when their request for a video arrives, because the request arrival rate based threshold $T=W(pref)$ keeps IS-STREAMING flag of the video true. This makes the requests to be served immediately

from the active chain by adding them to the existing chain. This scheme significantly reduces the client rejection ratio and request-service delay for the user as shown in the Figure 6.

The graph in the figure 7 shows that, our scheme uses significantly less server bandwidth. Popularity based Prefix caching approach and dynamic buffer allocation technique with the proposed streaming scheme helps the system to cache prefix of more number of videos. Also the requests arrival rate based threshold $T=W(pref)$ allows more number of clients to join the existing active chain. This maximizes bandwidth usage between the clients and hence reduces the average server bandwidth usage.

Figure 7 Bandwidth usages V/s Time

5. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have proposed an efficient video streaming scheme. The simulation results of this proposed scheme has demonstrated that, with the popularity based threshold $W(pref-1)$ allows more number of clients to get benefited from the existing active chain. Also the proposed prefix caching technique with dynamic buffer allocation algorithm has significantly reduced the request rejection ratio and client waiting time. The network bandwidth usage also has been reduced by sharing the video data of the currently played video object with other clients of the active chain. The future work is being carried out to recover the failure of any client of the existing active chain for the video by introducing a network management system, which will enhance the performance our proposed scheme.

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